

Synthesis of Arylhydrazono-tetrazolopyrimidones, -thiazolopyrimidones, -pyrazolopyrimidones and -benzimidazolopyrimidines. Part-4†

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Manuscript received 5 July 1988, accepted 6 January 1989

Ethyl α -arylazo- β -oxobutyrate (1a-e) undergoes condensation with 5-amino-tetrazole, 2-amino-4-carboethoxythiazole and 3-amino-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one to give the linearly fused condensation products (2, 4 and 5). While the condensation of α -arylhydrazonoacetylacetone with 2-aminobenzimidazole gives the arylazobenzimidazolopyrimidines (7). The structures of the compounds were established by analytical and spectral methods.

AS a part of our studies directed towards the development of new arylhydrazono derivatives of pharmaceutical interest containing a bridgehead nitrogen atom^{2,3}, considerable attention has been drawn to the synthesis of several condensed heterocyclic systems, especially derived from tetrazole, thiazole, pyrazole and benzimidazole.

The condensation of 5-aminotetrazole with ethyl α -arylazo- β -oxobutylate (1) gave two possible structures 2 or 3. The ir spectrum shows only one carbonyl absorption and NH, and no absorption due to a CONH group of cyclic structure 3. The assignment of structure 2 is consistent with (i) the observations made in our previous publications², (ii) that in β -keto ester, the amino group attacks the methyl ketone first, then the ester group, to

give the arylhydrazonotetrazolopyrimidones (2a-e), (iii) ¹H nmr spectrum (2c) displayed signals at δ 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 8.3 (1H, s, NH) and 6.8-7.8 (4H, m, ArH) and (iv) ir spectrum (2c) showed the CO absorption at 1 690 cm⁻¹.

The reaction of 1 with 2-amino-4-carboethoxythiazole afforded the arylazothiazolopyrimidones (4) in good yield. The ir spectra showed absorption bands at 1 600-1 610 (C=N), 1 640-1 665 (C=O), 1 680-1 710 (CO ester) and no (NH). The ¹H nmr spectrum of 4a displayed signals at δ 1.35 (3H, t, CH₃ of ester), 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.4 (2H, q, CH₂ of ester), 5.4 (1H, s, CH olefinic) and 7.35-7.5 (5H, m, ArH). The mass spectrum of 4e gave an M⁺ at 387 which fitted exactly with the calculated molecular weight.

Condensation of 1 with 3-amino-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one gave two possible structures 5 or 6.

a ; R=H, R'=H
b ; R=CH₃, R'=H
c ; R=Cl, R'=H
d ; R=Br, R'=H
e ; R=OC₂H₅, R'=NO₂

a ; R=H
b ; R=4-Cl
c ; R=4-Br
d ; R=4-CH₃
e ; R=3-NO₂

† For Part 3, see Ref. 1.

Based on the ir spectral data and our previous findings we favour structure 5 rather than 6. The ir spectra showed absorptions at 3 500–3 400 (OH), 1 680–1 700 (C=O of pyrazolone), 1 610–1 635 (C=N) and 1 595–1 600 cm^{-1} (N=N). The ^1H nmr spectra of 5b displayed signals at δ 2.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3), 14.1 (1H, s, OH) and 7.1–7.5 (9H, m, ArH).

In connection with the above successful reaction, it seemed of interest to react α -aryldiazoacetone (7) with 2-aminobenzimidazole in 5% sodium hydroxide solution to give the arylazobenzimidazolopyrimidines (8a–b) in good yield, as inferred from the absence of any absorption due to carbonyl or NH. The ^1H nmr spectra of 2a displayed signals at δ 2.1 (6H, s, 2CH_3) and 7.15–7.4 (9H, m, ArH).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer, and ^1H nmr spectra on a Jeol Fx90 Q FT spectrometer.

6-Aryldiazo-5-methyl[1,2,3,5]tetrazolo[5,1-a]pyrimid-7-one (2a–e). *Method-A*: A mixture of ethyl α -aryldiazo- β -oxobutyrate (1; 0.01 mol) and 5-aminotetrazole (0.01 mol) in xylene was refluxed for 24 h in presence of catalytic amount of piperidine. After cooling, the resulting precipitate was filtered, washed well with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), dried and crystallised from the appropriate solvent to give compounds 2a–e (Table 1).

Method-B: A mixture of ethyl α -aryldiazo- β -oxobutyrate (1; 0.01 mol) and 5-aminotetrazole (0.01 mol) in ethanol was refluxed for 16 h in

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2, 4, 5 AND 8*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p.** °C	Mol. formula (Mol. wt.)
2a	70	96 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₇ O (256.24)
2b	65	190 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₇ O (269.268)
2c	65	>260 ^a	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₇ OCl (289.689)
2d	70	160 ^a	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₇ OBr (334.48)
2e	80	175 ^b	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₉ O ₄ (344.3)
4a	65	155 ^a	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ SO ₂ (342.366)
4b	70	95 ^a	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SO ₂ Cl (376.313)
4c	70	148 ^a	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SO ₂ Br (421.272)
4d	60	65 ^b	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ SO ₂ (356.396)
4e	75	222 ^b	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₆ SO (387.366)
5a	70	120 ^b	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₂ Cl (379.797)
5b	60	95 ^b	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂ (359.38)
8a	55	172 ^b	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₅ (301.84)
8b	75	167 ^b	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₅ (315.87)

*All compounds showed satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis. **Solvent for crystallisation: ^aethanol, ^bdilute ethanol.

presence of catalytic amount of piperidine. After cooling, the resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with petroleum ether, dried and crystallised from the appropriate solvent to give compounds 2a–e.

6-Aryldiazo-4-ethoxycarbonyl-7-methylthiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidin-5-one (4a–e): The experimental conditions previously used to effect condensation of 1 with 5-aminotetrazole were adopted for the preparation of 4a–e via condensation of 1 with 2-amino-4-carboethoxythiazole (Table 1).

5-Aryldiazo-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-3-oxo-2-phenylpyrazolo[5,4-a]pyridine (5a, b): The above experimental procedures were adopted for preparation of 5a,b using 1 and 3-amino-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (Table 1).

3-Aryldiazo-2,4-dimethylpyrimido[1,2-a]benzimidazole (8a, b): The compounds were prepared by adopting the general procedure of treating 1 with 2-aminobenzimidazole using xylene–piperidine or ethanol–piperidine (Table 1).

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